

LINGUISTIC ASSERTIVENESS

A PRACTICAL GUIDE TO OWN YOUR
LANGUAGE

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TEN

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CBT: cognitive behavioural therapy

DL: dominant language(s)

LA: linguistic assertiveness

ML: minority/minoritised language(s)

Presentation

In this manual, readers will find brief theoretical explanations to why minority/minoritised language speakers (ML speakers) feel sometimes stressed to use their own language, why certain dynamics between DL speakers (DL speakers) and ML speakers tend to be the prevalent pattern, and what can be done to change these situations. In other words, this is a handbook designed to help readers understand more about language assertiveness (LA) and learn about resources that can be used to promote it. Our ultimate goal is to provide ML language speakers with tools that may help them to use the language in a practical, comfortable way. This will hopefully lead them to expand the contexts in which they speak it with confidence.

This handbook is designed for all ML speakers but it can also easily be used to help trainers design valuable resources which will boost the confidence of their students to use the language naturally and confidently in various social contexts. Promoting LA through the training of trainers is a powerful tool since trainers are the ones who can foster attitudes and behaviours that will contribute to protecting and promoting their ML.

This is not intended to be a masterpiece on how to proceed in all kinds of situations, nor is it intended to be a holy book on how to be a 'true' ML speaker. In this manual, the reader will find several resources that can be adapted to one's particular situation, interests and preferences. Please keep in mind that not all of them will be fitting for everyone. Each speaker should decide which resources are more suitable for their particular situation, or how they feel most comfortable using them. In fact, the proposal here is that, based on the analysis of one's own linguistic situation, the ML speaker can establish a personalised plan of goals and resources. There are no universal goals, no infallible methods, and no unique and non-transferable techniques. This is just a showcase of resources and each ML speaker will acquire what can best meet their needs.

BLOCK 1

WHAT DO YOU NEED TO KNOW? THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The psychological concept of assertiveness

Before we explore the concept of linguistic assertiveness, we will need to understand the construct of assertiveness. The Concise Oxford Dictionary defines assertiveness as: “Confident and forceful behaviour” (Assertiveness, 2019). On March 18th 2021, Wikipedia defines assertiveness as: “a method of critical thinking where an individual speaks up in defence of their views” (“Assertiveness,” 2021). Assertiveness means standing up for your personal rights, as well as expressing your thoughts, feelings and beliefs in direct, honest and appropriate ways. When we are assertive, we are forthrightly and positively expressing a will for **the recognition of our own rights**.

It is worth noting that being assertive never means to be aggressive. We are firmly expressing our opinion while understanding that other people also have the right to do so. Therefore, an assertive approach means expressing one’s thoughts, feelings and beliefs, while respecting the thoughts, feelings and beliefs of others (Peneva & Mavrodiev, 2013).

This is a skill that permeates various areas of the personal and professional spheres of an individual. Assertiveness has been applied to pedagogical practice in secondary school and in higher education (Bell, McGrane, Gunderson, & Anderson, 2011; Christopher, Edwards, & Eppler, 2012), in human resources and company management (Cheney, Christensen, Zorn, and Ganesh, 2010), sports, medicine, politics, religion, art, fashion, and all

disciplines which require a certain level of social competence and negotiation (Pachter & Magee, 2001).

Opposed to assertiveness, we would have those attitudes that are characterised by imposing opinions and views in an aggressive and reckless way, as well as submissive positions in which one does not have enough confidence to share one's opinions for fear that it may offend or annoy others.

Non-assertive behaviours fall into two main categories: aggressive and passive.

- Being **aggressive** means trying to fulfil your goals by means of threatening, attacking and/or manipulating other people.
- Being **passive** means to renounce your own goals in the benefit of others.

Neither of these two positions would be desirable when it comes to achieving effective communication and negotiation.

Ethical issues may be raised to object to aggressiveness, although there is also the matter of efficacy. This can be effective if applied to submissive individuals, and it may be so for limited periods of time. When tried upon non-submissive people, it will probably lead to a conflict escalation. On the other hand, passivity is a not at all desirable stance since it prevents the individuals from reaching their legitimate goals.

The assertive style would be placed right in the middle of both inadequate styles. It means renouncing to attack/manipulate other people, but it also implies that we do not renounce to reach our goals, provided that they are legitimate and don't imply violating other people's rights or dignity.

Figure 1. Passivity-Aggressiveness-Assertiveness

Because we cannot control how other people react to our actions, assertiveness training is oriented to build up ways to express ourselves in ways that are not intended to attack, upset or manipulate other people. In this context, training in assertive communication is the main tool to learn to maintain an honest position with one's own wills and desires, and in the face of the defence of one's own rights.

Communicating assertively means being direct, determined, and confident in initiating interaction, while being aware and respectful of the wishes of others.

Communicating in a non-assertive manner can fall into the category of acting aggressively or acting passively, which often means not acting at all. Communicating aggressively means being coercive, manipulating, and imposing our own views on an issue. Communicating passively means being resigned and adopting a position of submission.

Figure 2. Assertive communication vs. non-assertive communication

How does assertiveness relate to language use?

Assertive communication refers to the verbal (structure, words), as well as to the non-verbal content (voice intonation, speech's speed, body posture, facial expression...), which are more appropriate or convenient to transmit the intended message.

Applied to the languages' sphere, being assertive means learning to express yourself through your ML in social situations, while feeling at ease and comfortable. Considering the specific nature of MLs, it will involve learning to deal with common situations such as somebody questioning your right to speak your own language, or the interlocutor expressing lack of understanding or being dismissive or disrespectful to you.

A key element of this approach is that this is **a non-ideological position** to language choice. In most cases, MLs are subjected to ideology-based prejudices. A very common strategy oriented to reduce MLs social usage is to associate them with a particular ideology (nationalism, separatism...). Nevertheless, the approach proposed here is based on aspects that can be shared by all ML speakers, regardless of their ideology, and based on the assumption that languages (dominant or minoritised) should **not be used as political weapons**. If someone speaks a language, and particularly when it is a native language from the region where they live, their attempts to use it in as many social situations as possible should never be considered secondary to any political agenda. People are free to adhere to whatever ideology they consider worth it, but this fact should not affect their right or ability to speak through their language of choice.

Linguistic assertiveness means expressing yourself in your language with ease and comfort, while respecting the interlocutors, free from any type of threat, coercion or manipulation

The assertiveness approach will emphasise non-ideological reasons to speak the language. In fact, one of the main strengths of the assertive style is learning to give as few explanations and/or justifications as possible. Learning to control your own verbal and non-verbal behaviour does help a lot to do that.

Why is linguistic assertiveness important?

As ML speakers, you can sometimes feel that using your language in certain situations can be disadvantageous. It is quite common feeling stressed when having to choose whether we stick to our language —running the danger of not being understood and being reprimanded for it— or switching to the DL —increasing the probability of feeling discomfort for having given up an opportunity to use your language—.

The atypical situation of the ML can provoke a considerable amount of stress in the speaker when ...

Having to choose between two unpleasant options:

Sticking to the ML.

- DISCOMFORT → danger of not being understood and/or being reprimanded for it.

Switching to the DL.

- DISCOMFORT → having given up an opportunity to use the ML language, contributing to the reduction of its use

In almost each language exchange situation, a ML speaker will have to choose, increasing the probability of experiencing a certain amount of stress because of it. This situation of having to choose between two unpleasant situations and

experiencing the feeling of having little options can be linked to a psychological term known with the name of '**learned helplessness**'. This will be explained in more detail in the following sections.

Faced with these **discomfort-discomfort situations**, in which it seems that there is no successful exit, ML speakers may end up adopting the posture of 'defence speakers'. In similar future situations, it is likely that they display an attitude of passivity to avoid this unpleasant situation of having to be worried that they will not be understood or will be misjudged. Faced with these **risk-risk situations**, in which it seems that there is no successful exit, ML speakers may end up adopting the position of quietude. Therefore, we will adopt a position of what we call **linguistic submissiveness**.

Linguistic submissiveness can be seen through:

- Starting conversations systematically in the DL.
- Answering in the DL when addressed in this language.
- Switching to the DL when identifying that the other interlocutor is a DL speaker.
- Not speaking at all in a group to avoid having to make the choice between using the DL and using the ML.

To get out of linguistic submissiveness one of the most powerful tools is assertiveness.

Linguistic awareness, linguistic loyalty and linguistic assertiveness

It may be that when you read about the term linguistic assertiveness, at some point, you are thinking about someone who is clearly a firm speaker of ML. This person may have a clear conviction of the need to use the ML to contribute to its preservation, and they may be one of those people who openly expresses their love for it. But being aware of the situation of the language and even adhering to a position of linguistic loyalty, does not necessarily imply being linguistically assertive.

At this point, it is worth differentiating between three terms that are often considered synonymous yet they are not. These very similar terms are: linguistic awareness, linguistic loyalty and linguistic assertiveness. They are often confused and/or used interchangeably, but they are linked to three different language attitudes and, more importantly, to three different language behaviours.

Linguistic awareness: according to the [ALA](#) (Association for Language Awareness), it consists of "explicit knowledge about language and conscious perception and sensitivity when learning, teaching and using a language".

Linguistic loyalty: the willingness of a speaker not to abandon the use of the language of the linguistic community to which he or she belongs. It tends to connect with the pride in belonging to a given linguistic community.

Linguistic assertiveness: using the ML in different social situations, while feeling at ease and comfortable. Changing your linguistic habits to adopt a confident and direct attitude when using the ML.

One is built on top of the other, and generally they follow an evolving pattern: linguistic awareness is at the base of the process and it is necessary to develop linguistic loyalty, the state in which most ML activists are. However, linguistic loyalty is not enough to live comfortably with the ML. As will be explained in the following sections, lower use of the ML and dominance of the DL are established after certain dynamics which are mainly unconscious and constitute what we can call **linguistic habits**. Habits are something rooted in our brains and are often difficult to change. That is why being loyal to the language is not always enough to increase its use and it is **breaking the linguistic habits** we acquired through socialisation and education that can provoke this growth.

So, if habits are to an extent incrustated in our physique, how can we change them? From a psychological point of view, a habit is a quick response which emerges from a process whereby context prompts action automatically. In other words, it occurs when an exposure to a cue automatically triggers a non-conscious impulse. Generally speaking, **habits are necessary from an evolutionary perspective** since behavioural automatic responses require less cognitive overload. That frees some cognitive resources for other functions which might require more attention. The counterpart is that strong habitual tendencies will tend to dominate over motivational tendencies.

Linguistic behaviour is a habit too. That is good and bad news. Bad news is that it is mechanical, often robust, and full-integrated into our repertoire of automatic behaviours. Good news is that they can be eliminated or modified using the proper procedure. Developing assertiveness can help us to change our linguistic habits and to live more comfortably with the ML. To move from linguistic loyalty to linguistic assertiveness we cannot rely merely on motivational factors (sensitivity, awareness, willpower, intention, ...) but it needs **understanding the mechanisms of habit formation and habit modification**. Furthermore, we need resources to acquire new linguistic habits and substitute old patterns. This is essentially what this manual is aimed at. We want to provide the reader with the resources and strategies to become more assertive at using the ML.

Learned Helplessness

The concept of learned helplessness was coined in Seligman's theoretical model (1975). It is a **psychological state** that appears when an individual repeatedly experiences a situation in which they feel that their actions

do not generate the desired results. That is, their actions do not influence the outcomes. In short, it is **a feeling of lack of control over our environment and the circumstances that surround us**. Learned helplessness is one of the psychological constructs that has aroused the most interest in the last 15 years.

This phenomenon sharpens and crystallises when, even after the situation is later modified and it is already possible to control the environment, the individual persists in doing nothing because their actions have no effect. When an individual experiences learned helplessness, the pattern of action in the face of adversity becomes chronic. In this context, the preferred pattern of coping adversity is characterised by **freezing, blocking, fleeing, avoiding, or simply not coping**.

When a person shows learned helplessness it is evidenced by deficits on four levels:

- Emotional: fear.
- Cognitive: thoughts of defeat.
- Physiological: activation of the sympathetic branch of the nervous system.
- Behavioural: freezing and blocking.

It is important to remark that this pattern of behaviour is not characteristic of a person or of a specific situation. Different people in the same situation can develop this state, while others manage to overcome adversity and do not carry out this type of attribution of helplessness.

How does learned helplessness relate to speaking a minority language?

Speakers of MLs can suffer from 'learned helplessness', which often leads to subordinate and submissive behaviours.

This feeling of helplessness appears because, on the one hand, if we change to the DL, we feel that we are perhaps doing something out of social pressure and not with total comfort (and contributing to language substitution); and, on the other hand, if we do not switch and stick with our ML, then the chances that we will have to deal with confrontational situations increase: people will ask us why we do that, the conversation might drift into linguistic issues without being this our priority, etc.

But speaking a ML should not be limiting, blocking or paralysing. It should be an enjoyable experience rather than a source of stress. Despite the fact that many ML speakers experience these aversive feelings, it is possible to reverse this situation if one learns to identify these situations and incorporate strategies to deal with them successfully.

Can helplessness be unlearned?

Any learned behaviour is susceptible to being modified. A good way to fight this feeling of helplessness is relearning different strategies that help us feel capable of dealing with the complicated situations that may arise from maintaining the ML.

These strategies are summarised in the adoption of an assertive linguistic attitude, expressing our position of wanting to maintain the language in a clear, safe and not aggressive or passive way.

How do we acquire linguistic habits?

If we want to understand the mechanisms behind the acquisition of linguistic habits, we might first answer the following question: How do we generally acquire habits?

Habits emerge from cue-action associations rooted in behaviourist principles (classical conditioning and operant conditioning) and through repetition. According to behavioural principles and operant conditioning behaviours are acquired through **reinforcements and punishments** (see Table 1).

Table 1. Theoretical background: OPERANT CONDITIONING

<p style="text-align: center;">POSITIVE REINFORCEMENT</p> <p>Increases the future probability of a behaviour by offering a reward when the behaviour is exhibited.</p> <p><i>Example: "The owner of a dog offers a treat when the animal relieves itself in the proper place"</i></p>	<p style="text-align: center;">POSITIVE PUNISHMENT</p> <p>Decreases the future probability of a behaviour by applying an aversive stimulus when the behaviour is displayed.</p> <p><i>Example: "A mother reprimands a child for lying"</i></p>
<p style="text-align: center;">NEGATIVE REINFORCEMENT</p> <p>Increases the future probability of a behaviour by stopping, removing, or avoiding a negative outcome or aversive stimulus.</p> <p><i>Example: "A teacher reduces or eliminates homework if students study hard and achieve certain results in class"</i></p>	<p style="text-align: center;">NEGATIVE PUNISHMENT</p> <p>Decreases the future probability of a behaviour by removing a pleasant stimulus.</p> <p><i>Example: "A mother removes mobile phone from a teenager for bad grades"</i></p>

How do operant conditioning principles apply to linguistic habits?

Historically, using the DL has been positively reinforced, since it tends to attract the good kind of attention. At the same time, it has been negatively reinforced, since using the DL ensures that aversive situations (not being understood, being mocked...) will be avoided. On the other hand, using the ML has historically been positively punished, when speakers feel that they have been judged unfairly, and it has been negatively punished if the needs of the ML speaker are disregarded.

Given the positive reinforcement associated with the DL, the speakers (remember that all ML speakers are bilingual: they've had to learn the DL) know that by using it they are more likely to be successful in a given interaction (purchasing an item, submitting documents, getting directions, etc.). At the same time, the use of DL has been –and still is– negatively reinforced (reminder: in this context 'negative' does not mean bad, but 'absence of'), when the ML speakers know that using the DL will give them the respite of not having to deal with a potentially unpleasant situation. In that sense, the use of the DL has been negatively reinforced because it frees us from unpleasant situations.

Historically, using the DL has been:

Positively reinforced → more likely to be well treated.

Negatively reinforced → avoidance of discomfort.

Historically, using the ML has been:

Positively punished → unfairly judged (peasant, ignorant, low-class...).

Negatively punished → disregarded (ignored, rebuked...).

Table 2. Mechanisms of punishment and reinforcements applied to linguistic behaviour and submission

<p style="text-align: center;">POSITIVE REINFORCEMENT</p> <p>By using the DL we know that the interaction is more likely to be successful. The goal of the communicative exchange will be achieved: for example, the purchase of an item.</p> <p>This would work as a positive reinforcement for the DL use.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">↑ the use of the DL</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">POSITIVE PUNISHMENT</p> <p>ML's use is punished positively when we are judged unfairly. For example, when we perceive that we are considered illiterate or lower class.</p> <p>The fear of being considered illiterate or lower class would work as a positive punishment against ML's use.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">↓ the use of the ML</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">NEGATIVE REINFORCEMENT</p> <p>By using the DL we avoid those potential inconveniences that can sometimes appear when we use the ML. For example, being unfairly judged or disregarded.</p> <p>The avoiding of the potential criticism would work as a negative reinforcement for the DL use.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">↑ the use of the DL</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">NEGATIVE PUNISHMENT</p> <p>It could be that using the ML we cannot be understood (or the interlocutor feels like they do not want to understand) and therefore we might end up failing in the goal of the interaction: doing a purchase, asking for information.</p> <p>The failure of the purpose of the interaction would work as a negative punishment for the ML use.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">↓ the use of the ML</p>

Punishment does not have to be a dramatic measure, very visible, cruel or causing pain. A milder but constant punishment (as in making someone feel uncomfortable) can be as effective as blunt action.

Having a small stone in your shoe doesn't really hurt, but in the end you end up taking off your shoes to relieve yourself.

The discomfort, however slight, is a very powerful punishment because it is constant. You don't have to be attacked every time you speak ML, if they often show a bad face when you use your language, this is effective as a punishment because we will try to avoid the inconvenience.

Just being forced to repeat can be considered as a mild punishment because it increases the cost of the interaction.

In the case of linguistic behaviour the reprimand is to be consistent because the conditions are usually maintained over time.

However, and despite all the hostile contexts speakers of ML have been subjected to, the language has not been extinguished because there are some reinforcers which have favoured its maintenance (subtle reinforcers).

These reinforcers, although subtle, can be very effective:

- When you use your ML language you can identify other ML-speakers (your in-group).
- When you are considered "one of us" that will make others treat you in a certain way and that might put you in advantage over other individuals.

Why do people switch to the dominant language so quickly in certain situations?

Imagine a situation in which a ML speaker, for example Welsh, enters a local shop in the Welsh-speaking area where they know that the staff speaks Welsh, yet they start to speak English, the DL. Then, that person is displaying a type of behaviour which can be described as switching to the DL.

Psychologists have a name for this switching behaviour: submissiveness. Submissiveness is a spontaneous, self-induced suppression of a certain behaviour in favour of another one by virtue of habit, or of fear of punishment (understood from a psychological point of view). **Linguistic submissiveness** happens when people stop speaking their ML and switch to the DL, even when no-one has asked for it.

A common situation of linguistic submissiveness happens when two ML speakers, for example two Irish speakers, are having a conversation and then a stranger approaches them. Then, they switch to English (the DL), even if no one has said anything about the language. Very often, they do that not only while addressing the newcomer but also when they talk to each other. They are being linguistically submissive and that will contribute to making their language invisible: the newcomer may not even realise that another language was being spoken before his arrival.

We generally learn linguistic submissiveness from our parents, teachers and other figures of reference (that means that we might also learn linguistic assertiveness from them). These people serve as models to us. Through these models, we come to consolidate prejudices and we might as well adopt certain habits in favour of proactive linguistic behaviours.

There are many forms of language submissiveness. All of them have the potential to induce anxiety in the speaker and often tend to trigger a feeling of failure and helplessness (learned helplessness). Good news is that **language submissiveness is a behaviour**, a habit, and therefore, it can be changed.

How to do that? A behavioural change can emerge from the implementation of the principles of Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT), which serves as a theoretical framework for the acquisition of strategies that will help achieving behavioural changes: from linguistic submissiveness to linguistic assertiveness and ownership.

The principles of CBT are explained in the following sections. For now, and based on these principles, we can say that this linguistic habit change can occur if we do something that can be branded as “beating our *reflex brain*” (Compernelle, 2014). When speaking, **most people use their *reflex brain* when it comes to making a choice which language to speak.** That is very logical. Having conversations is a common occurrence. It takes extra energy to make a conscious decision about our language choice all the time. That is why our brain creates habits. A lot of ML speakers created the habit of starting in the DL when they are outside their ML bubble.

The *reflex brain* detects patterns at the speed of light, uses a lot of unconscious shortcuts, is guided by habits, relies on firm beliefs that are difficult to change, is black and white (no compromises), does not require conscious attention or willpower and therefore takes little brain power, and takes over when you are tired or insecure. When you want to change your linguistic behaviour (or any other behaviour), you have to make use of your *reflective brain* to implement those changes. On the other hand, the *reflective brain* makes conscious decisions, is proactive and focuses on goals, can deal with a lack of consistency, is rational, can master habits, can deal with nuances and compromises, requires conscious attention and willpower and therefore takes more brain power.

Using our *reflective brain* takes more time, effort and energy. After some time and with practice our brain will make new connections because we have learned new behaviours, by starting every conversation in ML for instance. We then can rely on our *reflex brain* again.

The benefits of starting every conversation through the ML, including replying to people in ML when approached in the DL [when your language is mutually intelligible with the DL] are:

1. It becomes a habit. You don't have to think about your language choice in every situation, which saves energy. Your reflex brain does the job for you.
2. You do what feels right for yourself and your language.
3. You will end up having many more conversations in your language, sometimes even in unexpected situations.
4. You will be more relaxed about bilingual conversations and become better at it (it will become a habit as well).
5. You will have more meaningful and interesting conversations, even with people who can't speak your language.
6. You will start to experiment more with your language choice in other situations and see it as a game. Using your language will feel less stressful and more fun.

The truth is that DL speakers are very unlikely to find themselves in a situation like that of ML speakers. Although it is generally accepted that knowledge is better than ignorance, and possessing skills (such as being able to speak more than one language) is better than lacking them, in some cases having less options can be more advantageous. Let's consider a couple of those:

- (a) You are a pedestrian in a crowded street where cars are constantly going along at a very low speed and not respecting the zebra crossing. If your intention is reaching the other side of the street, would you look at the driver (so acknowledging that you have seen the car)? Wouldn't it be more effective just looking ahead and acting as if you were not aware of the car? Showing (even faking) ignorance is stronger than displaying knowledge.
- (b) This is (fortunately) a more theoretical point: let's imagine that two drivers are going one against the other. One of them is blindfolded while the other can see and is aware of the blind condition of his counterpart. Which of them will get out of the way? This case shows that

having less options (being blindfolded) forces the one having more options to give way.

Referring to languages' interactions it can be concluded that being more ignorant (knowing only —or pretending that you only know— the DL and not the ML) is a stronger position since it forces the interlocutor to react, which —in many cases— would be equivalent to switching to the DL.

ML speakers have **the virtue of being able to choose**, because they are able to speak both languages. Although it should be considered as a superior condition (knowing is better than ignoring; being able is preferable to lacking the ability), from a pragmatic point of view, the DL speakers' ignorance (real or fake) becomes a strength.

Are you ever going to see this as a disadvantage? Despite the learned helpless/submissive linguistic behaviour and the repetitive punishment/reinforcement dynamics ML speakers have experienced through the years, it can still be said that they can choose to change. Different ways can be implemented to change their behaviour and choose when to use which language, in order to feel aligned with their preferences and needs. Being able to choose highlights the fact that deciding on speaking a language does not mean renouncing to the other one. It is a matter of preference, knowing that normally ML speakers have the ability to use both the ML and the DL and that speaking the ML does not eliminate the ability to speak the DL whenever they may decide to do so.

Assertive communication requires building up a positive image of your own ML. In other words, it means that speaking through the ML must be approached as an advantage rather than a disadvantage. From a positive perspective, being an ML speaker implies the fact that you have the capacity to choose a language. Similarly, being assertive means to consciously make decisions related to the choice of language.

Changing linguistic habits and choosing assertiveness

Learned helplessness is an attitude, which means a tendency to behave in a certain way. As such, it was once acquired, which means that it can be eliminated, re-learned or **modified**. A good way to combat this feeling of helplessness is to **relearn different strategies** that help us feel capable of dealing with the complicated situations that may arise from maintaining the ML.

These strategies are summarised in the adoption of an **assertive linguistic attitude**, expressing our position of wanting to maintain the language in a clear, safe and not aggressive or passive way.

Cognitive Behavioural Therapy

Cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) is a form of psychological treatment that has shown to be effective for the most common psychological disorders, such as depression, anxiety or alcohol and drug problems, among others. CBT has been developed on the basis of both scientific research and clinical practice. Research studies have shown CBT to be equally or more effective than other forms of psychological therapy or pharmacological treatment.

CBT's main principles can be summarised as follows:

- Psychological problems partly rely on faulty ways of thinking, as well as on learned patterns of self-damaging or unhelpful behaviour.
- Individuals can learn better ways to cope with psychological problems, which will reduce their symptoms and help them manage their lives more effectively.

CBT treatment usually focuses on modifying thinking patterns by means of strategies such as:

- Learning to recognise the thinking patterns and distortions that are producing our problems and learning to reassess them in light of reality.
- Learning to use problem-solving skills to cope with difficult situations.
- Learning to increase confidence in one's own abilities.
- Acquiring a better understanding of other people's behaviour and motives.

CBT treatment also promotes efforts to change behavioural patterns by means such as:

- Facing one's fears instead of avoiding them.
- Modifying the way certain situations are interpreted (cognitive restructuring and practice of new cognitive habits).
- Using role playing to prepare for potentially problematic interactions with others.
- Learning to calm one's mind and relax one's body.
- Keeping a tape record of their own behaviour (video or audio) to have feedback.

CBT is clearly focused on helping individuals learn to help themselves. For that purpose, exercises during the therapeutic session as well as exercises outside the sessions are performed, in order to help the patients to develop adequate coping skills that will make it easier to change their own thinking, undesired emotions and behaviour.

Although some information about the patient's past may be needed, CBT is clearly focused on the patient's current life and oriented to moving forward in order to develop more effective ways of coping with it.

BLOCK 2

PROMOTING LINGUISTIC ASSERTIVENESS: A PROPOSAL FOR ACTION

Why is speaking your language important?

There will be some ML speakers who rarely start a conversation with an unknown person in their language because they are not in the habit of doing so or because they feel unsafe or unconfident to do so. If someone has always used the DL, starting a conversation in ML might cause considerable discomfort.

When ML speakers switch into the DL, out of feeling uncomfortable and/or because they are afraid of not being understood, they are perpetuating the situation of abnormality of the ML. Then, they will realise that the ML is little spoken and that it is unlikely that they will be understood. Consequently, they will probably choose not to use the ML, which will increase the perception of “abnormality” associated with speaking through the ML.

This vicious circle has to be broken in order to recover a situation of normality for any ML. By gaining confidence and becoming linguistically assertive, ML speakers are **breaking this cycle** and recovering the possibility of contributing to the ML’s ability to be used in a variety of social contexts. But being linguistically assertive is not only beneficial for the collective of ML speakers as a group, as it betters the social situation of the language, but it also has individual advantages.

Short summary

- ML speakers feel uncomfortable speaking in the ML so they switch to the DL. That increases ML’s abnormality.
- They do that because it serves us as an adaptive behaviour. They experience no problems when they use the DL.
- This vicious circle can be broken by gaining linguistic assertiveness.

Changing linguistic habits: two approaches to the social use of RMLs

Top-down approaches come from governments and institutions and need decisive policies that are effectively applied. Laws, normatives and regulations are clear examples of top-down measures. The outcomes of top-down strategies are not immediately perceptible and they are more effective in the long-term.

High-Impact Modelling techniques may be effective as top-down strategies. They work when referents display the desired behaviour, in this case consistently using the ML. These public referent individuals can be politicians, successful athletes, artists or other celebrities.

Top-down support is fundamental, but is there anything that speakers can do?

Bottom-up approaches are the ones rooted in ML speakers' behaviour. When the speakers use the language in a variety of social situations, they are objectively creating the necessity of understanding it. This approach is complementary to top-down strategies. Both are very unlikely to succeed without the involvement of each other.

Government support is fundamental, but is there anything that speakers can do?

Low-Impact Modelling techniques are available to everybody, even if they are not famous or highly influential. They work at different levels: family, school, social groups, sport teams, school, but only if consistently applied by a critical mass of individuals. Speakers must feel comfortable when using the ML. Otherwise they will not persist when facing challenging situations and bottom-up actions will probably not succeed.

Setting up a workshop on linguistic assertiveness

When setting up a workshop, several questions must be considered. Which would be the groups that would potentially be interested in this type of training? How is it recommended that the physical space be organised when carrying out these workshops? What would be the best way to organise the time and in which parts can the sessions be divided?

(1) Build a group

Target groups

- Local and regional government
- Care and health organisations
- Schools and teachers
- Companies
- Interested people (for example from villages, sport or cultural associations, community initiatives)

It's important to know the target group to adapt the workshop depending on what the group needs.

Are they experienced trainers? Are they activists? Are they generally interested? Do they have to follow the workshop for work?

Setting

- It would be recommended that the workshop is conducted in a room (or location) designed for it.
- This space must have enough space to rearrange the tables and chairs and work in a small group, as well as sit in a circle.

Participants

- It would not be advisable to exceed 20 participants per group

Duration

- Around 3 hours
- 'Coffee break' somewhere in the middle of the workshop.

(2) Develop self-awareness

Once we have the group ready to start, where to start? A good place to start is by helping the group understand their own linguistic behaviour.

As mentioned in previous sections, linguistic submissiveness is a habit. As such, it can be modified or replaced. But first, to be able to change a behaviour we must assess it in the form it has at the moment. This will be the starting point for the change. We will invite the participants to explore how assertive-passive-aggressive they are in their language use in the ML. To do that, we suggest this language assertiveness test:

[Linguistic Assertiveness Self-Assessment](#)

Once everybody does have the chance to reflect about their own linguistic behaviour, we will invite the participants to identify in which situations they switch into the DL. You can use the following diagram to do that:

I generally switch to the DL when the interlocutor ...

These situations painted in green are situations in which there is no need to change the language because all supposed indicators that we will not be understood are probably not true. At least, we do not have the certainty that that will be so. The behaviour of switching to the DL is 'all on the ML speaker'. He was not asked to change the language (politely nor impolitely), he had no clear indistinct signal that he was not understood. He changed the language without any real need to. The yellow area is representing the situations in which the interlocutor verbally states that they do not speak the language, which does not mean they cannot understand. We considered that this is an

amber situation (and not red) because the interlocutor did not say that they do not understand the language. They just said that they are not able to speak it. Not until we get to the red sections, where explicit statements about not understanding the language or explicit demands about a language switching are made, we consider that the language change is somehow aligned with the situation. For the other situations, the switch was unnecessary.

The diagram of the traffic-light is very useful to encourage participants to: (1) honestly put themselves in one of the boxes, and (2) set the objective of jumping to the following tread.

(3) Devise alternatives

There are plenty of specific resources that you can use to be more linguistically assertive. For now, we'll learn three very simple ones: (1) Pole position; (2) Bilingual conversations; (3) Assertive demands.

1. Pole position

There is one simple thing you can start doing: to start a conversation in your ML.

When you meet a group of people, just greet them through the ML, loud and clear. Do not use generic formulas (Hi, Hello, Hey...) but a clearly identifiable local greeting expression (Bore da, Dia dhuit, ...). That way, you will be able to identify all the ML-speakers present. In some cases, most of them will be ML-speakers.

2. Bilingual conversations

Some people you already know are perfectly able to understand your ML, even if they are not fluent enough to speak it. That is a good opportunity for you to practise bilingual conversations. Additionally, it will help them to improve their knowledge and fluency and, eventually, the conversation might evolve towards the ML on both sides. If this is not the case, it will provide you with valuable experience in holding your language.

→ **Keep a record of your progresses**

When you practise a new habit it is important to do what we call a behaviour log. Keeping record of our behaviour allows us to easily detect changes and facilitate progress. Use the following record of bilingual conversations to do that. You will see how you feel more and more comfortable each time!

Table 3. Bilingual conversation chart

	M O N D A Y	T U E S D A Y	W E D N E S D A Y	T H U R S D A Y	F R I D A Y	S A T U R D A Y	S U N D A Y
Week from ___ to ___							
Bilingual conversations							
Degree of effort (0-10):							
Degree of satisfaction (0-10):							

Perceive bilingual conversations as **a game**, rather than a conflict. When we experience something in a pleasant way, we allow it to act as a reinforcer. And we already know that behaviours that provide reinforcement are more likely to repeat themselves.

Take a look at this YouTube video! They are consciously having a bilingual conversation.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=b757t82WjdY&t=225s>

3. Assertive demands

Think of the people with whom you already have a relationship of any kind (acquaintances, neighbours, co-workers, friends, family, couple ...), which so far has been developed in the DL. Think about how many of these conversations could be held by you in the ML. How would you do that without necessarily making them change their language of precedence? How would you do that so that it is not too uncomfortable? Is there a way of making it in a smooth way?

This can be done in different styles. Here, we will learn how to employ assertive demands to switch to the ML and keep your language in different conversations.

Characteristics of an assertive demand for language change:

1. Formulate it in the first person without manipulating or providing more reasons, and prepare your argument based on fully subjective reasons: "I would like", "I would prefer", "I would feel better", "I would like to", "I would be more comfortable if...".
2. Do not ask it as an ultimatum, but as a negotiated solution: What do you think? How does it sound to you?
3. Response Prevention: Anticipate the other person's more probable response. "In what ways is he likely to tell you no?" and then, prepare your next answer to that.
4. Reach a viable compromise. Example: *"You can keep speaking Dutch and I will continue in Frisian. Let's see how it goes".*

Recommendations for assertive demand which lead to language change:

1. Select the time and opportunity (on what day, under which conditions) when you will expose the request to the person in question. Generally, it is advisable to do it without other people being present.
2. Present it in a way that highlights the positive elements. For example: "I am used to speaking the ML with those people I respect and love. I would like to do the same with you."
3. Prepare your answers, because you are likely to find some resistance there.

→ ***Keep speaking your language whenever you are understood!***

PROGRAMMING A WORKSHOP: AN EXAMPLE

This section is aimed to present a proposal of how the programming of one session for the workshop might look like. Please note that this is only a general guide, and considerations for the specific sociolinguistic situation of the ML, and the specific profile of the participants should be taken into account, so that the way the sessions are designed can be as personalised as possible.

That said, a session can have the following sections:

1. Welcome: explanation of the programme
2. Presenting the psychology behind changing language habits
3. Real life situations: Exploring the participants' linguistic habits
4. What will be the next steps? Resources and strategies
5. Classroom practices
6. Make a personal action plan
7. Closure

1. Welcome: explanation of the programme

Strike the right note!

It is important to approach this subject as something very interesting for everybody. Because it is about communication and personal well being in the first place. We want to stay away from a moral or ideologically-focused discussion.

The welcome can start with the question **“What does language mean to you?”**. Everybody should be able to answer freely. Every answer will be allowed.

Watch out! Listen to everybody, don't react or start a discussion.

This is a way of getting everybody involved that is used in Deep Democracy. Deep Democracy is an attitude that focuses on the awareness of voices that are both central and marginal. Unlike “classical” democracy, which focuses on majority rule, Deep Democracy suggests that all voices, states of awareness, and frameworks of reality are important.

Keep in mind that the general goal of this welcoming sections is to set the starting point for the worksop, establish the framework and define what participants can and cannot expect, but also (1) to make sure the participants are focused on the topic, that they are ‘present’ and (2) to help them let go of the outside world (worries, work) for a while and live positively the linguistic habit change.

After this big first question, we can proceed by saying that this is a workshop about language, multilingualism and in particular the phenomenon of ML speakers switching to the DL. We also tell a little bit about the Listen project and how ‘being silent’ in your own language as a minority speaker is a universal phenomenon.

These are some of the questions that can be asked:

- Are we really using the ML as much as we think/want?
- Why do we switch to the DL? And when?
- Have you ever heard about 'linguistic submissiveness'?
- How do we acquire our linguistic habits? How do we become linguistically submissive?

2. Presenting the psychology behind changing language habits

Then, we can proceed to tell the participants about the psychology behind language use, about why we do what we do, if we can change that and how we can change our behaviour.

To begin this second part we suggest a little reflection around a fictitious territory which we call the Veridian Republic. In the Veridian Republic there are two languages in contact: Veridian and Cramovinian. But these two languages are not equal, since one of them tends to dominate while the other tends to remain in a state of submissiveness. The inhabitants of this territory apply the following rule: whenever there is a Cramovinian speaker in a conversation between two or more people, the interlocutors will use the Cramovinian language. In this way, in a conversation with two people both speaking Veridian, Veridian will be spoken. If one of them speaks Cramovinian, the predominant language will be Cramovinian. In a three-person conversation, as long as there is a Cramodian speaker, the exchange will take place in Cramovinian, even if there are two people facing a Veridian speaker. That way, and applying the same dynamics, a large percentage (64%) of conversations will take place in Cramovinian, even when in the Veridian Republic there are more Veridian (75%) than Cramovinian (25%) speakers.

Veridian	Cramovinian
A B C	D
A B	C D
A C	A B C
A D	A B D
B C	B D C
B D	A B C D

This hypothetical situation will probably rise the reflexion over the fact that these dynamics of dominance and submissiveness easily lead to a more and more reduced use of the language, which at the same time contributes to the scenario of one of the languages being less used, and consequently increasing the probability for its speakers to feel odd when using it. This results in an endless cycle of lower rate of use of the language, more abnormality, less presence and more conversations conducted in the DL as it is illustrated by the following figure (see section *Why is speaking your language important*).

The vicious cycle of MLs

The question which seems to be following this last reflection is: Why do we feel uncomfortable using the ML? Thus, we will proceed by presenting this type of linguistic submissiveness by means of talking about how we acquire linguistic habits according to conditioning principles (see section *How do we acquire linguistic habits?*) and how due to these principles, the DL was socially promoted while the ML was socially punished. Furthermore, you can discuss the concept of learned helplessness and how it applies to linguistic submissiveness (see section *Learned Helplessness*).

The “Presenting the psychology behind linguistic change” step of the workshop can end in a very organic way with the explanation of how language behaviour has nothing to do with having a positive attitude towards our language or being aware of the importance of our language (see section *Linguistic awareness, linguistic loyalty and linguistic assertiveness*). It is about habits, and habits are unconscious behaviour (see section *How do we acquire linguistic behaviours*). That means that if you want, you can change your habits/behaviour (see section *Changing linguistic habits and choosing assertiveness*).

3. Real life situations: Exploring the participants’ linguistic habits.

This section can begin with questions such as: *How do you do it when meeting a non-ML speaker?*

Then, some real-life situations, including personal experiences and anecdotes must be shared and commented on. It is crucial to keep a firm grasp on the timing. This section can take forever if every participant gets free reign to explain their personal anecdotes. Those are useful to illustrate the principles and to increase personal involvement (motivation). Nevertheless, if the trainer does not exert an effective control, not only time will fly but also a sort of negative mood can get generalised. Many ML speakers will have sad

experiences that –if put together– are likely to convey a certain degree of pessimism.

After just a few of these personal experiences, we can start dealing with other self-centered questions such as *Why do we feel extra uncomfortable as ML speakers?* or *In which types of situations do we switch to the DL?* and *Why do you think we do that?*

Then, the traffic light diagram (see section *Develop self-awareness*) can be used to properly place the personal experiences and the circumstances that tend to prompt the submissive behaviour.

4. What will be the next steps? Resources and strategies

Next, you might want to stress that as speakers we must take several considerations or guidelines to frame assertiveness training: cognitive frame and communicative frame.

Bellow, you will find a brief list:

1. Cognitive tools
 1. Put aside your own prejudices and assumptions
 2. Change your self- dialogue (what you say to yourself)
 3. Use self-instructions

2. Communicative tools
 4. Start through the ML as the default mode (you will at all times be able to switch)
 5. Use both verbal and non verbal communication
 6. Frame and reframe

7. Stay away from ideological arguments

This will set the mental framework which will serve as a reference for the classroom practices and the eventual acquisition of resources to achieve assertiveness.

5. Classroom practices

Now it is time to practice everything. To do that, you can find some classroom practices that you can use (see section Classroom practices).

6. Make a personal action plan

Changing language habits is not exclusively dependent on having a positive attitude towards the language or being aware of the importance of using the ML, since habits are automatic and often not conscious. Changing language habits means changing behavioural habits, which requires adopting certain strategies, gaining some few resources and switching past patterns.

To move **from awareness to a linguistically assertive behaviour** we must consider three important moments in communication:

- A. The moment we decide which language we use (and what do we tell ourselves then).
- B. The moment we react to what the other person says (what do we say and how we do it).
- C. The moment we are aware of how we feel at that moment.

When our objective is to achieve linguistic change (this is, habit change) the first step is to be aware that habits can be divided into smaller behaviours.

For example, the habit of eating a bag of chips is constituted by several consecutive discrete sub-actions: (1) opening bag, (2) putting hand in bag, (3) putting food in mouth, (4) chewing, (5) swallowing.

In this sense, habits are constituted by a set of smaller behaviours in a sequence in which one behaviour automatically triggers the next. So the first guideline for the personal action plan is to set one objective and deconstruct it into a series of discrete sub-actions.

Table 4. Objective setting chart

Objective:		ANTECEDENT: Cue-action association	CONSEQUENT: Reinforcer
Sub-action 1			
Sub-action 2			
Sub-action 3			
...			

Let's see an example. It could be applied to a new speaker who has achieved relative fluency and wants to practice the language with native speakers.

Objective:		ANTECEDENT: Cue-action association	CONSEQUENT: Reinforcer
Sub-action 1	<i>Greetings</i>	<i>Approaching the waiter</i>	<i>Waiter's smile</i>
Sub-action 2	<i>Asking for a drink</i>	<i>Pointing out to the beer tap</i>	<i>Tasting the beer</i>
Sub-action 3	<i>Small talk</i>	<i>Catching the waiter's look</i>	<i>Feeling included</i>

Another way of approaching this section may be the following:

1. Think about a number of situations in which you want to change your language behaviour. For example, with a neighbour, a colleague, at the coffee bar, communicating with your local government, on the sports field.
2. Rank every situation from 1 - 10 (1 = easy; 10 = very difficult)
3. Make a plan.
 - Choose which situation you want to start with (tip: choose the situation which is most easy for you).
 - Write down your target (for example, I want to speak my language, I want to answer in my language).
 - When will I do (date, time of the day, every day 5 minutes, every time when I...), where will I do it?
 - How will I do it? What if...?
 - What will I save for next time, what will I do differently next time? (evaluation)

7. Closure

→ *The workshop should end with a positive tone*

The acquired resources should be summarised, better by the participants than by the trainer. The idea that *having more resources gives us extra degrees of freedom* is generally a good one to finish with. Also, it is of the essence reminding that the job is not done by attending the workshop. The real job is working on yourself in order to introduce a new language-selection habit. Keeping records and being in touch with other assertiveness learners may be generally a good idea. The trainer should offer as well a way to get in touch for further doubts or comments.

CLASSROOM PRACTICES

Make an assertive request

Think of a request to make to some of your classmates.

Put it this way:

- ★ Aggressive
- ★ Passive
- ★ Assertive

Verbal vs. non-verbal communication

Generally when we want to express confidence, we do that both verbally and non-verbally. If you want to display a certain image it is more likely that what you express non-verbally gets more attention from the interlocutor and unconsciously will dominate how the message will be received.

When we want to express a demand with confidence we will have to show confidence non-verbally too. Especially non-verbally. Because the non-verbal

communication, which is often forgotten, is the most important part of any interaction. This is something that can and must be practised.

Think of different messages you can convey to the rest of the group but deliver it using different non-verbal cues. Thus, you will be practising how to better control non-verbal aspects of communication.

Practise specially assertive non-verbal communication.

What is assertive non-verbal communication like?

- Look directly at the interlocutor
- Active genuine listening to the interlocutor/s
- Relaxed posture
 - Arms are relaxed beside the body
 - Head is erect between the shoulders
 - Shoulders are relaxed
- Expressions on your face, and your eyes open to listen, friendly (eye contact with a smile)
- Do not look down or away much
- Loud and clear voice (yes, this is 'voice' but it still is non-verbal)

Defence against criticism

What to do when we are verbally attacked (disqualifications, insults, humiliations, taunts ...)?

Improper ways to defend yourself:

1. Return the attack → it will lead to an escalation (we don't want that).
2. Give justifications → it will weaken our position and legitimate the attack.

3. Excuses (I don't know ... it's not up to me ...) → it will show us as puppets who are not in charge of our own behaviour.

First of all, you should pay attention to the following figure.

It is quite easy to tell apart demand from attacks. A demand can always be answered by means of an action, even if it is incorrectly formulated. “Give me the salt” would be an impolite way to ask for it in a social gathering but it could be, nevertheless, satisfied by an action consisting in handing them the salt. It might also be met by an answer on the lines of “Would you mind asking me for it politely?”, but the bottom line is that a demand can be always responded with a motor action.

On the other hand, an attack cannot be solved by means of any action. If you are told “You are a linguistic extremist” or “I’ve got enough of your silly obsession”, there is nothing you can do to respond to these statements with an action. Thus, they are attacks and all the attacks should be neutralised and –if possible– extinguished (the attack, not the attacker!).

An inappropriate demand, either issued in an unproper way (not polite enough) or by someone who is not our legitimate interlocutor*, can be either extinguished (not attended) or redirected (addressed to the proper target). Let us see an example.

You are queuing in a grocery shop. When it is your turn you address the foreign-looking clerk through your ML. Someone behind you intervenes and says "Have you not seen he's a foreigner? Why don't you speak English to him?"

What would be your answer? If you get involved in this dialogue, you would be legitimating the other customer's right to getting in your way. Redirecting or deflecting that interruption might take the form of saying something on the lines of: "Sorry, it is my turn now" and –at the same time– turning your back on them and facing the clerk. That way, your verbal as well as your non-verbal behaviour would be effectively communicating the same message: *you are not welcome into this conversation.*

As for the attacks, all of them should be extinguished. 'Extinction' is a psychological term which means taking out every source of reinforcement (reward). When someone attacks you, their main satisfaction would be making you feel badly (affected, unbalanced, uncomfortable, uneasy...). Thus, the way to avoid giving them that sort of satisfaction (reward) would be not to show any kind of emotional disturbance. This might sound extremely difficult to master but it is not. In this section you will learn just a few techniques that you can apply as if you were playing a game. If you focus on the technical aspects of it you will experience all these situations as something playful and easy to cope with.

Some self-defence techniques:

1. Fog wall

To any attack (“You’re just a radical”, “Your language-obsession is boring”...) we will respond with a neutral non-verbal expression accompanied by saying something on the lines of “Maybe” or “You might be right” or “That’s possible”. It might seem a simple thing (maybe even a silly thing) but try it and see what happens. The attacker is expecting a response (protesting, arguing...) that shows your emotional discomfort, but they are getting none!

2. The dictionary technique

You just have to focus on a single word of what your attacker said and ask them about its meaning. Let’s say the attack was *“You are just a bunch of radicals”*. Your answer should be something like: *“What do you mean by ‘radical’?”*. Then, no matter what the answer is, you will focus on another word and do exactly the same. Let’s suppose that their answer is: *“A radical is someone that’s obsessed with a single issue”*. Then you should replay something on the lines of: *“And what do you exactly understand by ‘Obsessed’?”*. It is highly improbable that they will go on that way. Most probably, you will get something like *“It’s impossible to have a serious conversation with you”*, to which you should respond by applying technique #1: *“You might be right!”*.

Remember that your objective is not convincing anyone but extinguishing the attacking behaviour. If the attacker falls back into an honest conversation style, we will probably be happy to engage in a civil conversation.

3. The *"you're right"* technique.

That one is really simple. You just have to answer *"You're right"*, *"You're absolutely right"* or *"I couldn't agree more with you!"* to any received attack. Of course you may object that you would be giving up that way but... are you sure? Maybe *you're absolutely right!*. Or aren't you? Let's see an example. You are told:

- *"Hey, you should speak English and not your bloody dialect!"*
- *"You're absolutely right, mate!"* (while you keep speaking your ML)

Do you really think they will feel you've given up?

4. Exaggeration

On the same lines, and if you happen to favour a more ironic style, you may add up a grain of salt and say something on the lines of: *"Radical, you say?... No way! I'm the #1 public enemy!"*.

Again, the principle is the same one: they are expecting a reaction from you and they are not getting it! In fact, they are getting the opposite of a resistance: you are pushing in the same direction, which makes it difficult to keep pushing. That's exactly what 'extinction' means... in the psychological parlance.

There are a few more techniques but these ones will be enough for the speakers to get out and try them. They should build up their own strategies based on these ones. It is generally enough if they rehearse one of the techniques and practise it in combination with the fog wall.

Conclusion

This handbook's aim was to provide theoretical as well as practical resources to build up ML speakers' assertive attitudes. That means that they will be able to display assertive behaviours in relation to speaking their own language at home. If we carefully think about it, it is quite weird to feel ashamed of speaking one's language ... whenever at home! Nevertheless, we have seen that this is not a shameful thing but something we all (ML speakers) have learned, no matter where we are located and which is our language.

Now, it is all about rehearsing and getting really skilled. As any other ability, it has to be practised. First, it should be rehearsed in favourable situations, as any other skill. Go out and do it while feeling protected friends and/or in situations that could be rated as 'easy to solve'. Then, challenge yourself with more daring social interactions and keep being linguistically assertive. The more practice, the easier it will get. And when you manage to really feel comfortable while maintaining your LM, then you will become a model for others, and this is the most powerful strategy we can come up with. Much more than preaching or explaining, modelling is the ultimate way of disseminating the behaviour we need in order to keep our languages alive and thriving.

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ANNEXES

Stories of linguistic assertiveness

"I always start a conversation in my own language and believe it's the counterpart's responsibility to inform me that he/she does not understand. I also continue speaking my own language if I know they understand, even if they reply in any other language. I'm also in politics, and if I have a meeting in Sami areas or with some governmental representatives, I expect them to have interpreters with them. If they don't, then they have to come back later. "

A., Northern Sami speaker

"Speaking with others, I try to set a good context for communication. I let them clearly know that to me it is perfectly normal to speak my language. As well, even if my counterpart avoids using his own language, switching to the majority, I also keep talking to him in my language, encouraging and supporting an appropriate response on his part."

N., Sardinian speaker

"It is true that I have already set up a routine where Spanish is barely spoken in my daily life. However, it is also true that whenever I walk into a shop, as I live in a quiet Spanish speaking environment, and I feel linguistic stress I might not address in Basque directly."

B., Basque speaker

"I speak Sardinian every day at home and at work. I speak exclusively Sardinian to my son. I try to speak Sardinian at every occasion, but I switch to Italian whenever the other person replies in Italian. "

G., Sardinian speaker

"When talking with people whom I know are Sardinian speakers, I start the conversation in Sardinian, even on formal occasions if possible. If the

interlocutor replies in Italian, I alternate the two languages trying to go back to Sardinian. Sometimes the other speaker "gives in", especially if the topic of the conversation is familiar, while I notice a certain difficulty with more complex and more technical topics, which require linguistic skills not limited to the vernacular. In those cases I have often found myself forced to retranslate concepts just expressed in Sardinian into Italian: at that point I continue in Italian, resuming with Sardinian at the first useful opportunity. With interlocutors unknown to me, but certainly Sardinians: I make my debut quite often in Sardinian, especially in informal contexts, based on the answer. However, I try to use expressions in Sardinian interspersed with Italian even when the interlocutor, even if he limits his expression to Italian, shows at least a passive competence in the Sardinian language."

M., Sardinian speaker